

REMEDICATION INSTRUCTION FOR AN IMPROVED READING ABILITY: BASIS FOR PROGRAM MANAGEMENT OF GRADE 1 PUPILS

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ABSTRACT

Reading Remediation instruction is frequently used as a way to assist struggling pupils and bring their reading skills from K – 3 before deciding on the best way to provide instruction. This study focused on Remediation Instruction for an Improved Reading Ability: Basis for Program Management of Grade 1 Pupils. The respondents of the study were the sixty-six (66) Grade 1 pupils of Prudencia D. Fule Memorial Elementary School who underwent reading remediation at the start of the school year with a pre-assessment of prior knowledge until the second assessment in December 2020. The researcher-made questionnaire was adopted from various sources. The majority of the respondents were aged 7 to 8 and were female. The result of the study shows that respondents observed that reading materials, activity sheets and study guide were important aspects for reading remediation instruction. This means that the perception of the respondents to these three (3) remediation instruction contribute significantly to the child's reading journey. After the reading assessment of the respondents, 61 of them assessed as high and average performance while only 5 pupils attained a low performance rating. Despite of the big changes in the way children learn and read because of the pandemic, very few are still performing poorly; therefore, The null hypothesis, “Is the remediation instruction in reading significantly related to the pupils’ reading ability in terms of reading fluency” is not sustained. Likewise, the null hypothesis “Is the remediation instruction in reading significantly related to the pupils’ reading ability in terms of reading comprehension” is not sustained in these undertakings.

Keywords: Remediation, Reading, Ability, Pupils, Fluency, Comprehension